

real client = the client package that we executed the release's test.

-> means nested providers from the real client. For example **p**->**p2**@x.y.z means that **p2** is the **p**'s provider and **p** is the real client's provider.

1) `escope@3.4` changed a key in its code, that did not introduce an error, but it became incompatible with `babel-eslint`. The `escope` **is not** a `babel-eslint`'s provider. This error was fixed by `babel-eslint@4.1.8`, when its providers [claimed](#) that it should be fixed in `babel-eslint`.

- [Issue in babel-eslint](#)
- [Issue in escope](#)
- [Pull-request in babel-eslint](#)
- Fixed by **provider** `babel-eslint`, which is the provider of the real client.
- Category: **incompatible providers version**.

2) the real client has `grunt-jshint->jshint@>=0.3.4` as its providers. The `jshint@0.9.0` started to use ES6 and moved all of ES5's code to another file. The `grunt-jshint@1.1.13` did a downgrade in the `jshint`'s version. Specifically, the `grunt-jshint` uses the array `JSLINT.error`, which was moved to another file. `jshint` is a provider of `grunt-jshint`, and `grunt-jshint` is a provider of real client.

- [Downgrade of jshint](#)
- [jshint@0.9.0 diff](#)
- [jshint@0.9.0 changelog](#)
- Fixed by **provider as client** `grunt-jshint`, which is the client of `jshint`.
- Category: **Feature change**.

3) the real client has the `babel-preset-es2015-rollup@6.24.1` as its provider. The `babel-preset-es2015-rollup` has the `babel-preset-es2015` as its

provider, that is introducing an error. The `babel-preset-es2015@6.13.1` introduced a new format that [became an error](#) in `babel-preset-es2015-rollup`, which had to fix this error in its version 1.2.0.

- [babel-preset-es2015@6.13.1 change](#).
- [babel-preset-es2015-rollup issue \(fix\)](#).
- Fixed by **provider as client** `babel-preset-es2015-rollup`, which is client of `babel-preset-es2015`.
- Category: **Feature change**.

4) `react@0.14` is not compatible with `prop-types@>15`. The real client uses the `react@0.14.6`. The real client also uses provider `rc-dialog@5.2.2 -> rc-align@2.4.5 -> prop-types@15`. The `react@0.14.9` fixes this incompatibility.

- [Prop-types compatibility](#).
- [react@0.14.9 fixes this incompatibility](#).
- Fixed by **provider** `react`, which is the provider of the real client.
- Category: **incompatible providers version**.

5) The real client has a provider `front-matter@0.2.0` that wrote a wrong code:

```
const pattern = pattern = '^(' // same var twice
```

The clients did a downgrade and, then, an upgrade.

- [pull-request](#).
- Client [downgrade](#) and [upgrade](#).
- Fixed by (first) **client** and by **provider** `front-matter`.
- Category: **Wrong code**.

6) The real client has a provider `grunt-testacular@*`. The `grunt-testacular@0.3.0` changed the task name from *“testacularServer”* to *“testacular”*.

Neither provider or client fixed this error.

- `grunt-testacular@0.2.0` [change](#).
- Category: **Feature change**.

7) The real client has a provider `nosql-memdb@>=0.11.3`. In release 0.11.4, `nosql-memdb` returned an object to callback. In release 0.11.5, this object was removed from callback, fixing the error. The real client updated to `nosql-memdb@>=0.11.5`.

- `abstract-iterator` [error](#) and [fix](#).
- real client [update](#) the `abstract-iterator` version.
- Fixed by **provider** `abstract-iterator`.
- Category: **Object type change** (*undefined* was returned, then a *new NotFoundError()*, then *undefined* again).

8) The real client uses `eslint@0.*` as its provider. The `eslint@0.16` changed the rule *no-comma-dangle* to *comma-dangle* and marked it as a breaking in changelog. The real client removed the `eslint` provider and replaced it with `standart`.

- `eslint@0.16` [changelog](#).
- The real client [replaced](#) the `eslint` by `standart`.
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

9) The `eslint-config-airbnb -> eslint-config-airbnb-base@^11.0.1` is the client's provider. The `eslint-config-airbnb-base@11.1.2` changed the rule *no-param-reassign* introducing a new property. This property just works with `eslint@^3.18.0`. The real client updated its providers to fix this error.

- `eslint-config-airbnb-base` [change](#).
- `eslint-config-airbnb-base` and `eslint` [compatibility](#).
- real client [fix](#).
- Fixed by **provider** `eslint@3.18.0` and then by the real client.
- Category: **Incompatible provider versions**.

10) the real client uses the `imagemin->imagemin-optipng@^4.0.0`. The `imagemin-optipng@4.2.0` changed the values in one array and broke the client.

This error was fixed by the client.

- `imagemin-optipng@4.2.0` [change](#).
- real client [fix](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

11) The real client uses the `react-redux-provide->react-redux@^4.0.0`. The `react-redux@4.2.0` removes its implementation of a function `isPlainObject` and starts to use `isPlainObject` directly from `lodash`. So, the client `react-redux-provide@5.2.0` fixes this error replacing the provider.

- `react-redux@4.2.0` [change](#).
- `react-redux-provide@5.2.0` [replacing](#) the provider to `is-plain-object@^2.0.1`.
- Fixed by **provider as client** `react-redux-provide`.
- Category: **Object type changed** (`isPlainObject` changed from the `react-redux`'s implementation to the `lodash`'s implementation).

12) The real client uses the `enzyme@^2.7.1` as its provider. The `enzyme@2.8.1` starts to support `react@15.5`, but it requires another dependency: `react-test-renderer`. Neither the real client or its providers have `react-test-renderer` as dependency. So, the client breaks. Then, `enzyme@2.8.2` fixes its code. Then, the real client adds `react-test-renderer` as its provider.

- `enzyme@2.7.1` [change](#).
- `enzyme@2.7.2` [fix](#).
- The real client [fix](#).
- Fixed by **provider** `enzyme@2.7.2` and after by client.

- Category: **Feature change** (it may be similar to an *incompatible provider change*, but I believe the enzyme@2.7.1 change did not become incompatible with no one).

13) The real client has `test-machinepack-mocha` -> `test-machinepack@^2.1.0` as its providers. The `test-machinepack@2.1.19` removes one of its providers and tries to implement its own code, to replace the provider. He implements your own `runInstantiatedMachine` object. The `test-machinepack-mocha` updated the `test-machinepack` to fix its code.

- `test-machinepack` [change](#).
- `test-machinepack-mocha` [update](#).
- Fixed by **provider as client** `test-machinepack-mocha`.
- Category: **Object type changed** (The object `runInstantiatedMachine` was changed to its own implementation).

14) The real client has the `esprima-extract-comments->esprima@git` (actually, this `esprima` is a fork for the original one) as its providers. The `esprima` added its main file, the `dist/esprima.js`, to `.gitignore`. So, `esprima-extract-comments` cannot import `esprima` directly from `git`. The `esprima-extract-comments` fixed it depending on `esprima` directly from `npm`.

- `esprima` [removes](#) and [adds](#) its file to `.gitignore`.
- `esprima-extract-comments` [fixes](#).
- Fixed by **provider as client** `esprima-extract-comments`.
- Category: **File not Found**.

15) The real client has the `fakeredis->redis@^2.4.0` as its dependencies. The `redis@2.6.0-1` changes the name of one function and breaks `fakeredis`. So, `fakeredis` does a downgrade to `redis@2.6.0` and fixes the error.

- `redis` [renames](#) function.
- `fakeredis` [fixes](#) `redis`.

- Fixed by **provider as client** `fakereidis`.
- Category: **Renamed Function**.

16) The real client has `jsdom@~0.10.5` as its provider. `jsdom` was created without a `set` method. So, when the `Array.prototype.splice` tried to set the `length` property, it broke. It was fixed by `jsdom@1.0.0-pre.1`, when a `set` method was created. The client did not fix anything.

- `jsdom` [fixes](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category: **undefined object**.

17) The real client has `@types/lodash-es->@types/lodash@*` as its provider. The `@types/lodash@4.14.122` changed the type of an object and broke the client's build. Neither provider or client fixed this error.

- `@types/lodash` [change](#).
- Category: **Object type change**.

18) The real client has `karma-remap-istanbul -> remap-istanbul -> source-map@>=0.5.0`. The `source-map@0.7.0` returns `new Promise()` instead of a previous object. The `remap-istanbul` did a downgrade in `source-map`.

- `source-map` [change](#).
- `remap-istanbul` [fix](#).
- Fixed by **provider as client** `remap-istanbul`.
- Category: **Object type change**.

19) The real client has `ember-cli -> broccoli-merge-trees -> broccoli-plugin@^1.3.0` and `ember-cli-qunit@^1.4.0` as its providers. The `ember-cli-qunit@1.0.4` changed the type of an object that was returned and it worked

well. Then, `broccoli-plugin@1.3.1` changed the way of validation the objects, and the object changed in `ember-cli-qunit@1.0.4` was not recognized. Thus, `ember-cli-qunit@1.4.3` fixed the object type to be recognized.

- `ember-cli-qunit@1.0.4` [change](#).
- `broccoli-plugin@1.3.1` [change](#).
- `ember-cli-qunit@1.4.3` [fix](#).
- Fixed by **provider** `ember-cli-qunit`.
- Category: **incompatible provider versions**.

20) The real client has `docpad->cson->js2coffee@~0.2.3` as its provider. The `js2coffee@0.2.6` changed the preinstall script to execute with `npm run-script` instead of `node`. In `js2coffee@0.3.1` it was fixed reverting the preinstall script to `node`. Then, `cson` updated to `js2coffee@~0.3.1`.

- `js2coffee@0.2.6` [change](#).
- `js2coffee@0.3.1` [fix](#).
- `cson` [update](#).
- Fixed by **provider** and by client (`cson`) after.
- Category: **Wrong code**.

21) The real client updated its `mongodb` provider from `1.2.x` to `1.3.x`. The `mongodb@1.3.13` changed the way an error should be emitted. So, the real client updates its code and `mongodb`'s version to adapt itself with the change.

- real client [update](#) `mongodb`.
- `mongodb@1.3.13` [change](#).
- real client updates `mongodb`'s [version](#) and its code.
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

22) The real client has `backbone@1.1.x` as its provider. The `backbone@1.1.1` changed one feature that broke the real client. The real client did a downgrade in the backbone's version until it was fixed, but did a change in its code to work well with the error. When `backbone@1.1.2` fixed the error, the real client updated backbone's version. Then, the real client did an upgrade.

- real client [downgrade](#).
- real client [fixes](#) to work with `backbone@1.1.1`.
- `backbone@1.1.2` [fixes](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

23) The real client has `cradle->request@2.x.x` as its provider. The `request@2.18.0` changed one feature introducing an empty field in the request body. The real client fixed this error removing the tests and the `cradle` as dependency.

- `request@2.18.0` [changes](#).
- real client [fixes](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

24) The real client updated the `window-stream` provider from `~0.4.0` to `~0.5.0`. The `window-stream@0.5.3` changed the returned object `new Date(/*just the parameter was removed*/)`. Then, the real client changed its code to work with the new `window-stream`'s change and update the `window-stream`'s version.

- real client [updates](#).
- `window-stream` [change](#).
- real client [recovering](#) and [updating](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

25) The real client has `ember-cli-htmlbars-inline-precompile@^0.1.1` as its provider. The `ember-cli-htmlbars-inline-precompile@0.0.1` started to use an undefined var. So, `ember-cli-htmlbars-inline-precompile@0.3.0` fixed it doing:

```
app.options = app.options || {};
```

Then, the real client updated the `ember-cli-htmlbars-inline-precompile`.

- `ember-cli-htmlbars-inline-precompile` [fixes](#).
- real client [updates](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category: **undefined object**.

26) The real cliente has the provider `ember-cli-qunit@4.0.0` -> `ember-qunit`, and they are incompatible. This incompatibility was fixed by `ember-cli-qunit@4.1.0-beta.1`.

- `ember-cli-qunit@4.1.0-beta.1` [fix](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category **Incompatible Providers versions**.

27) The real cliente has `ember-template-lint@2.0.0-beta.5` as its provider that changed one linting rule. The provider introduced and fixed the error in version `2.0.1`. So, the client updated the provider's version.

- `ember-template-lint@2.0.0-beta.5` [change](#).
- client [updates](#) the provider's version.
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category **Feature change**.

28) The real client update from `q@^1.0.1` to `q@^2.0.1` and it worked well. The `q@2.0.1` uses `collections@^2.0.0`, and `collections@2.0.2` removed the

'shims' supports and broke `q`. Then, `q@2.0.3` removed the collections. The real client, thus, downgraded `q` to recover the error.

- The real client [update](#) `q`.
- collections [change](#).
- `q@2.0.3` [removing](#) collections.
- The real client [downgrade](#) `q`.
- Fixed by **provider** `q`, which is the real client's provider.
- Category: **Incompatible providers versions**.

29) The real client has `react-foundation-components->foundation-sites` as its providers. The developer of `foundation-sites` published a release using a wrong version. He wanted to publish as beta, but it was published in `foundation-sites@6.3.1-rc1`, instead. It was fixed in `foundation-sites@6.3.2-rc2`, but it did not work for the real client. So, the real client did a downgrade in the `foundation-sites`'s version.

- `foundation-sites` [wrong publish](#).
- Real client [downgrade](#).
- Fixed by **client**, because the provider's next release did not work.
- Category: **Feature change**.

30) The real client has `eslint->js-yaml@^3.2.5` as its providers. The `js-yaml@3.5.0` does not accept duplicate keys in the yaml file. However, the `eslint` did not do anything about it, because they claimed it should be fixed only in `js-yaml`. No one fixed this error.

- `js-yaml@3.5.0` [change](#).
- `eslint` [claim](#).
- Category: **Feature change**.

31) The real client has `karma->socket.io@^1.3.7`. The `socket.io@1.4.0` changed one array to an object. This error was fixed in `karma` updating `socket.io`'s version and changing its code.

- `socket.io@1.4.0` [change](#).
- `karma` [changing](#) and [updating](#).
- `karma` [changelog](#).
- Fixed by **provider as client** `karma`.
- Category: **Object type changed**.

32) The real client uses `@babel/preset-env@^7.8.4` as its provider. The `@babel/preset-env@7.8.7` removed one of its providers and implements its own code. Then, the real client updated the `@babel/preset-env`'s version.

- `@babel/preset-env` [change](#).
- real client [update](#).
- Fixed by no one.
- Category: **Object type change**.

33) The real client uses `afn@^1.2.7` as its provider. The `afn@1.3.0` changed the way of determining the plugin names. The real client did an upgrade to `afn@2.0.0-pre`.

- `afn@1.3.0` [change](#).
- real client [update](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

34) The real client uses `nodent@2.1.10->acorn-es7-plugin@^1.0.4`. The `acorn-es7-plugin@1.0.10` changed its code to work just with `acorn@2.6.x`. However, the `nodent@2.1.10` uses `acorn@2.4.0`. So, `nodent@2.3.6` updated both providers.

- `acorn-es7-plugin@1.0.10` [change](#).
- `nodent@2.3.6` [updates](#).
- Fixed by **provider** `nodent`.
- Category: **Incompatible provider versions**.

35) The real client has `nodent@3->acorn@>=2.5.2` as its providers. Due to the range, `nodent` received `acorn@6.0.5` and broke the build. Then, `nodent@3.2.10` removed the file that was used in `acorn`. The breaking change is raised by `nodent@3` which allowed breaking changes from `acorn (>=)`, but did not worry about the `acorn`'s breaking change. The client did an upgrade in `nodent` version.

- `nodent@3` [update](#) that accepts all `acorn`'s release.
- `nodent@3.2.10` [fix](#).
- Real client [upgrade](#).
- Fixed by **provider** `nodent` and real client, after.
- Category: **Outdated code**.

36) The real client has a provider `rc-overlay@0.0.8` that requires a `css` file in the `require()` function. This error was fixed in `rc-overlay@1.0.0`. Then, the real client updated the `rc-overlay`.

- Client [update](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category: **Wrong code**.

37) The real client has as its provider `broken-link-checker@0.7.6 -> parse5@3.0.3 -> @types/node@14.10.3`. The provider `@types/node@7.10.12` changed the type of an object. It was fixed in real client updating the provider `typescript@^3.3.3`.

- Real client [fix](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Object type changed**.

38) The real client has as its provider the `@types/lodash@4.14.160`, which one changed the type of an object. It was fixed by the real client updating the provider `typescript`. This case happened in the same releases of the previous case (38).

- Real client [fix](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Object type changed**.

39) The real client has its provider `eslint@4.19.0`, which improved its code to involve the TC39 Regex enhancements. The real client fixed this breaking change changing its code.

- `eslint@4.19.0` [changelog](#).
- real client [fix](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

40) The real client has its provider steady in `jsdom@16`, which one introduced a function to work with other providers. This function had an error and was fixed in `jsdom@16.3.0`, but the real client didn't receive this update. The `jsdom`'s provider `whatwg-url@8.2` introduced a feature to work with that function in `jsdom@16`, but the real client got an error because it didn't receive the `jsdom@16.3` updates.

- `jsdom` [changelog](#).
- `whatwg-url` [issue](#).
- Fixed by **provider** `jsdom@16.3`.
- Category: **Incompatible provider versions**.

41) The real client has its provider `assetgraph->terser@4.3.9`, which changed the way to do a parser. Then, the real client changed its code to work with the new `terser`'s release.

- terser [issue](#).
- real client [fix](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

42) The real client has its provider `assetgraph@5.7.0`, which introduced a breaking change in its code. This breaking change was fixed by `assetgraph@5.7.1` and by the real client.

- `assetgraph@5.7.0` and `5.7.1` [changelog](#).
- real client [fix](#).
- Fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

43) The real client has its provider `assetgraph@2.15.0`, which calls a function in its provider `normalizeurl`, but that function just exists in a further release of `normalizeurl`. The `assetgraph@2.15.1` fixed the error updating the `normalizeurl`. Then, the real client updated the `assetgraph`'s version.

- `assetgraph@2.15.0` [error](#).
- `assetgraph@2.15.1` [fix](#).
- real client [update](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category: **Wrong code**.

44) The real client has as its provider `optipng@0.3.0`, which by mistake renamed a function. The function was renamed back in `optipng@0.3.1`. The real client updated the `optipng`'s version.

- `optipng` [issue](#).
- `optipng@0.3.0` [renames a function](#).
- `optipng@0.3.1` [renames back](#).
- real client [updates](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.

- Category: **Renamed function**.

45) The real client has as its provider `stylelint@7.1.0` and `stylelint-config-primer@1.1.0` -> `stylelint-scss@1.5.2`. When `stylelint-scss@1.5.0` added a new rule, the provider `stylelint` broke. Then, the `stylelint-config-primer@2.0.0-0` updated the `stylelint`'s version.

- `stylelint-scss` [issue](#).
- `stylelint-scss@1.5.0` [add rule](#).
- `stylelint-config-primer` [update](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category: **Incompatible provider versions**.

46) The real client has as its provider `yeoman-generator@0.20.2` -> `yeoman-environment@1.6.0`, which introduced an error. `yeoman-environment@1.6.0` updated its provider inquirer but did not update its code to work with the new inquirer's version. This breaking change was not fixed yet.

- `yeoman-environment` [update](#).
- `yeoman-environment` [tried](#) to update its code.
- Category: **Outdated code**.

47) The real client updated `heroku-client@2.0.0` to `2.0.1`, and it introduced an error. There was an undefined variable in `heroku-client@2.0.1` that was fixed in `heroku-client@2.2.0`. Then, the real client updated the `heroku-client`'s version.

- real client [first update](#).
- `heroku-client@2.0.1` [error](#).
- `heroku-client@2.2.0` [fix](#).
- real client [last updates](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category: **Undefined object**.

48) The real client updated its provider `netrc-parser@3.1.1` to `3.1.2`, which introduced a breaking change. The `netrc-parser@3.1.2` changed one feature. It was fixed in `netrc-parser@3.1.4`. The real client updates the `netrc-parser`'s version.

- real client [first update](#).
- `netrc-parser@3.1.2` [change](#).
- `netrc-parser@3.1.4` [fix](#).
- real client [last update](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

49) The real client has its provider `joe@1.6.0` -> `event-emitter-grouped@2.5.0`, which introduced a breaking change. `event-emitter-grouped` changed one of its rules. `joe@1.6.1` fixed it changing the semver.

- `event-emitter-grouped@2.5.0` [change](#).
- `joe@1.6.1` [fix](#).
- Fixed by **provider as client**.
- Category: **Feature change**.

50) The real client has its provider `nanohtml@1.0.0`, which tried to get access in a wrong file path. It was fixed in `nanohtml@1.0.1`. Then, the real client did an upgrade in the `nanohtml`'s version.

- `nanohtml@1.0.1` [fix](#).
- real client [upgrade](#).
- fixed by **client**.
- Category: **Wrong code**.

51) The real client has as its provider `on-load@3.3.2`, which introduced a breaking change. The provider `on-load@3.3.2` forgot to adapt its code from Web to Node. This error was fixed in `on-load@3.3.4`, when the provider finally imported the `window` variable. The real client pinned the `on-load`'s version but updated it after.

- `on-load` [pull](#).
- `on-load@3.3.2` [change](#).
- `on-load@3.3.4` [fix](#).
- real client [upgrade](#).
- Category: **Undefined Object**.

52) The provider updated the provider `@typescript-eslint/parser@^1.1.0` to `^1.7.0`, which is incompatible with the provider `typescript@<3.2.1 >=3.5.0`. A breaking change was introduced in `@typescript-eslint/parser@1.6.0` and fixed in `@typescript-eslint/parser@1.10.0`.

- real client [first update](#).
- `@typescript-eslint/parser` [issue](#).
- `@typescript-eslint/parser@1.6.0` [changelog](#).
- `@typescript-eslint/parser@1.10.0` [fix](#).
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category: **Incompatible providers version**.

53) The real client has as its provider `cheerio@0.22.0` -> `dom-serializer@0.1.1`. `dom-serializer@0.1.1` introduced a breaking change removing the previous returned value within an object. No one has fixed this error.

- `dom-serializer` [issue](#).
- `dom-serializer@0.1.1` [change](#).
- Category: **Feature change**.

54) The real client has as its provider `rc-overlay` -> `react-dom@15.4.0`, which tried to get access in a file that did not exist in `react@<15.4`. `react-dom@15.4.0` inserted the `react` in the `peerDependencies` and `Node.js > 3` does not install `peerDependencies`. So, that required file did not exist. Then, the `rc-overlay` removed `react-dom@^15.6.1` and let `react-dom@^15` in the `peerDependencies`.

- `react-dom@15.4` [change](#).
- `rc-overlay` [update](#).
- an [issue](#) about.
- Fixed by **provider**.
- Category: **Incompatible provider version**.

55) The provider `tslint-config-airbnb@5.3.1` introduced a breaking change when updated its providers. Some linting rules were changed. It was not fixed by anyone yet.

- `tslint-config-airbnb@5.3.1` [update](#).
- Category: **Feature change**.